

DMP for the LZP FLPP project - "A Thirty-Year Study of Corporate Ownership Evolution in Latvia" (Izp-2024/1-0551)

Version 1

Description

This document is the initial version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the research project (2025–2027), conducted within the Fundamental and Applied Research Programme (FLPP) under project No. LZP-2024/1-0551, "A Thirty-Year Study of Corporate Ownership Evolution in Latvia" funded by the Latvian Council of Science. The DMP will be maintained as a living document using the Argos DMP tool, with regular updates uploaded to Zenodo throughout the project's duration. Revisions will be aligned with project milestones, interim internal evaluations, and the completion of each major work package.

The DMP provides a comprehensive strategy for managing the data collected and generated during the project. The project's primary aim is to advance scientific understanding of ownership and management transitions in Latvian private firms over the period 1991–2023, assessing how different ownership structures and transition models affect firm survival, financial performance, operational continuity, and workforce retention. The study focuses on key themes in corporate governance research, including the roles of passive and active owners, succession practices within family firms, and the long-term implications of planned versus crisis-induced transitions.

The project employs a mixed-method research design combining extensive quantitative data collection with complementary qualitative insights. The core dataset will be constructed by retrieving historical records from the Latvian Enterprise Register via its API, covering shareholder identities, ownership shares (direct and indirect), and management board information for more than 150,000 limited liability firms. This longitudinal dataset will capture ownership structures and transitions from the date of firm registration through 2023 or liquidation. In addition, more than 30 qualitative in-depth interviews with representatives of family-owned firms will provide deeper insights into the dynamics of passive and active involvement during transition periods.

The final research outputs will include an academic literature review paper, a coded longitudinal ownership dataset accompanied by a methodological manual, one or more academic journal articles, and a policy brief outlining evidence-based, context-sensitive recommendations to support successful ownership transitions, enhance firm survival, and strengthen business continuity in Latvia.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Fundamental and Applied
Research Programme (FLPP)

Researchers

Anete Pajuste (0000-0001-9108-9992), Valerija Kozlova (Feldmane) (0000-0002-5639-6396), Jelena Luca (0000-0002-1858-2059), Maija Dobele (0009-0008-8481-5181), Marija Krumina (0009-0006-7890-6445), Timurs Safiulins (0000-0001-7614-5554), Ricards Agapovs,

Gustavs Jānis Gauja, Mikk Saard, Saule Cibiraite, Davids Keziks,
Daniela Martinsone, Ignas Vaitekoniš

Organizations

Baltic International Centre for Economic Policy Studies (BICEPS)

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: DMP for the LZP FLPP project - "A Thirty-Year Study of Corporate Ownership Evolution in Latvia" (Izp-2024/1-0551)

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Ignas Vaitekonis

Organizations:

Baltic International Centre for Economic Policy Studies (BICEPS)

Contact: Jakobsone Lelde (lelde@biceps.org)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Fundamental and Applied Research Programme (FLPP)

Project: LZP-2024/1-0551

3. License

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Access Rights: Public

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4. Templates

Descriptions

A longitudinal dataset on corporate ownership and management evolution in Latvia (1991–2023)

The dataset documents the evolution of ownership structures and management composition of Latvian private firms over the period 1991–2023. It is constructed using historical administrative records retrieved via the Latvian Enterprise Register API and covers shareholder identities, ownership shares (direct and indirect), and management board membership from firm registration until liquidation or the end of 2023. The dataset supports longitudinal analysis of ownership transitions, succession patterns, and governance structures in a transition-economy context.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the data collection is to advance scientific understanding of ownership and management transitions in Latvian private firms and to assess how different ownership structures and transition models affect firm survival, financial performance, operational continuity, and workforce retention. The data originate primarily from administrative records provided by the Latvian Enterprise Register and are complemented by qualitative interview data generated within the project.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Event
- Administrative records data
- Textual data
- Other

Financial data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- XLS
- JSON

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

300

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The dataset will be useful to academic researchers in corporate governance, family business, and transition-economy studies; policymakers interested in business continuity and succession; and educators using real-world longitudinal data for teaching purposes.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

Yes

Comment:

Embargo period will be applied until scientific articles are submitted for publication and published as well as the final project assessment is finalised (i.e., till the beginning of 2031).

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org>

Zenodo is an open dissemination research data repository for the preservation and making available of research, educational and informational content. Access to Zenodo's content is open to all.

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Standard statistical and data-processing software such as R, Python or Stata.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

Creative Commons is a nonprofit organization that provides open licenses and legal tools to help researchers share their work. The license mandates that users give proper credit to the creator and permits them to distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the content in any medium or format.

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2031-01-01

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2131-01-01

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

All personnel expenses will be covered within the project "A Thirty-Year Study of Corporate Ownership Evolution in Latvia" (LZP-2024/1-0551).

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

- Anete Pajuste (0000-0001-9108-9992)
- Marija Krumina (0009-0006-7890-6445)

- Lelde Jakobsonsone

Project leader Anete Pajuste and researcher Marija Krūmiņa will handle the data description and processing. Research administrator Lelde Jakobsonsone will oversee the process and ensure it aligns with other activities while providing guidance.

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

The costs of making the data available via a repository are limited to the time researchers may need to prepare the data for archiving, so it's recommended to plan for this early while the project is still ongoing. Therefore costs will be covered within the project "A Thirty-Year Study of Corporate Ownership Evolution in Latvia" (LZP-2024/1-0551).

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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